

Effects of Plantain (*Musa Paradisiaca*) Diet on Flexion Reflex and Righting Reflex in Female Wistar Rats

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ABSTRACT

Musa paradisiaca (Plantain) fruit has been shown to be useful for nutritional, medicinal and industrial purposes. It contains serotonin (5-HT) and adrenaline. Serotonin plays a fundamental role in integration of behaviour and many physiological functions including regulation of mood, anxiety, arousal, aggression, impulse control, and change in contraction rate of muscles. Adrenaline also play a role in redistributing blood to the muscles, increasing blood pressure and expanding the air passages of the lungs. Twenty healthy female wistar rats (n=20) were divided into four groups and were administered water (control group), 10mg/kg (group 2), 20mg/kg (group 3) and 30mg/kg (group 4) plantain stock respectively. After ten days of administration, the neurobehavioral tests were carried out on the 11th and 12th day. The levels of neurotransmitter serotonin and adrenaline were evaluated, the data was analysed using one-way ANOVA (analysis for variance). Results are presented in mean \pm SEM (standard error of mean) and values of $p < 0.05$. For serotonin, results showed no statistical significant difference across the groups. Adrenaline showed no statistical significant difference across the groups as well. Both flexion reflex and righting reflex had no statistically significant difference for the first and second day. The rats fed with higher dose 30mg/kg of plantain diets had higher levels of serotonin and adrenaline and quick reflex action when compared to the other groups although no statistically significant difference was recorded.

Key Words: Effects, Plantain, Diet, Flexion Reflex, Righting, Reflex, Female, Wistar Rats

INTRODUCTION

Musa paradisiaca, commonly called plantain is a vastly cultivated food crop that constitutes staple diet in food of many populations. Plantain is rich in carbohydrates and fibre but lacks cholesterol. It contains vitamin A, B6, C and minerals; potassium, magnesium among others (Robinson, 1996). It also contains some neurotransmitters including dopamine, noradrenaline, adrenaline tyramine, octopamine and serotonin. Plantains (*Musa* spp., AAB genome) are plants producing fruits that remain starchy at maturity (Marriot and Lancaster, 1983; Robinson, 1996) and need processing before consumption. Plantain production in Africa is estimated at more than 50% of worldwide production (FAO, 1990). The majority (82%) of plantains in Africa are produced in the area stretching from the lowlands of Guinea and Liberia to the central basin of the Democratic Republic of Congo. West and Central Africa contribute 61 and 21%, respectively (FAO, 1986). It is estimated that about 70 million people in West and Central Africa derive more than 25% of their carbohydrates from plantains, making them one of the most important sources of food energy throughout the African lowland humid forest zone (Swennen, 1990). Nigeria is one of the largest plantain producing countries in the world (FAO, 2006).

The consumption of plantain has risen tremendously in Nigeria in recent years because of the rapidly increasing urbanization and the great demand for easy and convenient foods by the non-farming urban populations. Besides being the staple for many people in more humid regions, plantain is a delicacy and favored snack for people even in other ecologies. A growing industry, mainly plantain chips, is believed to be responsible for the high demand being experienced now in the country. This study reviews the trend of plantain production, its problems and prospects in Nigeria in the last two decades (Swennen, 1990).

Reflex is an involuntary and nearly instantaneous movement in response to stimulus. It is also an automatic response to a stimulus that does not receive or need conscious thought as it occurs through a reflex arc. Reflex arcs act on impulse before the impulse reaches the brain. (physopedia). The reflex arc governs the operation of reflexes. Nerve impulses follow nerve pathways as they travel through the nervous system. The simplest of these path ways, including a few neurons, constitutes a reflex arc pass through the spinal cord are called spinal reflexes.

Statement of Research Problem

The daily consumption levels of plantain boiled, fried and ripe banana were 225, 136 and 145 g respectively for children from Cameroon, while in Nigeria, the figure were 112, 82 and 80 g respectively. (academic journals). Even though it may seem UN important anxiety helps us to identify danger in fight or flight mode. The right amount of anxiety can help us perform better and stimulate action, importance of reflex is that it occurs without of thinking about them. They also

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allow the body to react in ways that help one to be safe stand upright and be active, memory is essential to all learning because it lets the individual store and retrieve information that is passed to the individual through learning. Hence, the aim of this project is to ascertain the effects of plantain diet on reflex.

Aim and Objectives

The aim of this study is to test if feeding animals with plantain diet has effects on reflexes in female wistar rats

Objectives of the research

1. Effects of plantain diet on reflex (righting reflex and response to pain stimulation)

Hypothesis

Consumption of plantain diet has no effects on reflex

LITERATURE REVIEW

Biology of Plantain

Musa paradisiaca is the accepted name for the hybrid between *Musa acuminata* and *Musa balbisiana*. Most cultivated bananas and plantains are triploid cultivars either of this hybrid or of *M. acuminata* alone. Linnaeus originally used the name *M. paradisiaca* only for plantains or cooking bananas, but the modern usage includes hybrid cultivars used both for cooking and as dessert bananas. Linnaeus's name for dessert bananas, *Musa sapientum*, is thus a synonym of *Musa paradisiaca*. Almost all cultivated plantains and many cultivated bananas are triploid cultivars of *M. paradisiaca*. It is believed that Southeast Asian farmers first domesticated *M. acuminata*. When the cultivated plants spread north-west into areas where *M. balbisiana* was native (see map), hybrids between the two species occurred and were then developed further into a wide range of cultivars. (Swennen, 1990).

Hundreds of cultivars of *M. paradisiaca* are known, possessing characteristics that are highly variable, but broadly intermediate between the ancestral species. They are typically 2–9 meters (7–30 ft.) tall when mature. The above-ground part of the plant is a "false stem" or pseudostem, consisting of leaves and their fused bases. Each pseudostem can produce a single flowering stem.

After fruiting, the pseudostem dies, but offshoots may develop from the base of the plant. Cultivars of *M. paradisiaca* are usually sterile, without seeds or viable pollen. (Nelson, S.C. *et al.*, (2006)

Banana plants were originally classified by Linnaeus into two species, which he called *Musa paradisiaca* for those used as cooking bananas (plantains), and *M. sapientum* for those used as dessert bananas. It was later discovered that both of his "species" were actually cultivated varieties of the hybrid between two wild species, *M. acuminata* and *M. balbisiana*, which is now called *M. paradisiaca*. The circumscription of the modern taxon *M. paradisiaca* thus includes both the original *M. paradisiaca* and *M. sapientum*, the latter being reduced to a synonym of *M. paradisiaca*. (*Musa paradisiaca*", World Checklist of Selected Plant Families, Royal Botanic Gardens, Kew, retrieved 2013-01-14)

In pre-Linnaean times this banana was named '*Musa serapionis*', for instance by Maria Sybilla Merian in her *Metamorphosis insectorum Surinamensium* of 1705. At one time, to deal with the great diversity of cultivated bananas and plantains, botanists created many other names which are now regarded as synonyms of *M. × paradisiaca*, such as *M. corniculata* Lour., (Swennen, 1990) used for a group of plantains with large fruit resembling the horns of a bull. Cultivated varieties are now given cultivar names, with the cultivars classified into groups and subgroups. Thus *M. × paradisiaca* 'Horn' is a cultivar belonging to the AAB genome group, Plantain subgroup.

Plate 1: Picture of plantain (business day.ng)

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Nutritional Benefits of Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*)

Plantains are a nutritious food item with many potential health benefits, such as being a source of vitamins, fiber, potassium, and antioxidants. Plantains (*Musa paradisiaca*) are a member of the banana family. They are a major food staple in Africa, and they also form part of the diet in Latin America. Unlike bananas, people usually cook plantains before eating them. Cooking methods include frying, baking, and boiling. People can also eat plantains at different stages of ripeness, from when the fruit is green through to when it is yellow and black. Drying and grinding green plantains produces a flour that people use in Caribbean and West Indian cooking.

Central Nervous System

Constantly alive with electricity, the nervous system is the body's prime communication and coordination network. It is so vast and complex that, an estimate is that all the individual nerves from one body, joined end to end, and could reach around the world two and a half times. The Brain and Spinal Cord are the Central Nervous System. The brain and spinal cord (the CNS) function as the control centre.

They receive data and feedback from the sensory organs and from nerves throughout the body, process the information, and send commands back out, Nerve pathways of the PNS carry the incoming and outgoing signals, The Spinal Cord Transmits Signals to and from the Brain and Commands Reflexes, The spinal cord is an elongated cylinder of neuron cell bodies, bundles of axons and other cells, protected by connective tissue and bone. It connects to the brain at the medulla oblongata and runs down the vertebral column, the hollow tunnel enclosed within the vertebrae of the spine. The spinal cord is part of the central nervous system and serves as a kind of superhighway. Sensory information and motor commands travel up and down, heading to and from the brain. These signals speed in and out of the spinal cord via spinal nerves—the “on-ramps and off-ramps” that branch out to supply the limbs, torso, and pelvis.

Spinal reflexes

A reflex is a rapid, involuntary, predictable response to a stimulus. Most reflexes are concerned with survival and defending the body against damage and harm, such as coughing to remove irritants from the lower airways and sneezing to clear the nasal airways. Spinal reflexes involve circuits of sensory nerve fibres that feed information to the spinal cord and then connect directly, or via an intermediate neuron, to motor nerve fibres, so that the resulting instructions for movement go directly out from the cord to the relevant muscles and not to the brain, to be activated. This is called a Reflex Arc.

The Brain and Areas that Control Reflexes

In some ways, the human brain resembles a computer.

But in addition to logical processing, it is capable of complex development, learning, self-awareness, emotion, and creativity.

Every second, millions of chemical and electrical signals pass around the brain and the body's intricate nerve network.

But nervous tissue is delicate and needs physical protection and a reliable blood supply.

The brain, in conjunction with the spinal cord, regulates both none conscious processes and coordinates most voluntary movement.

It is the site of consciousness, allowing humans to think and learn.

It is shielded by the three protective membranes (meninges) that envelop it, and the ventricles (chambers) in the brain produce a watery medium within the skull known as cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) that absorbs and disperses excessive mechanical forces which might otherwise cause serious injury. It turns out that the human brain is very fragile. The brain, in conjunction with the spinal cord, regulates both none conscious processes and coordinates most voluntary movement. It is the site of consciousness, allowing humans to think and learn.

It is shielded by the three protective membranes (meninges) that envelop it, and the ventricles (chambers) in the brain produce a watery medium within the skull known as cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) that absorbs and disperses excessive mechanical forces which might otherwise cause serious injury. The cerebrum is the largest brain structure and part of the forebrain (or pros-encephalon).

Its prominent outer portion, the cerebral cortex, not only processes sensory and motor information but enables consciousness, our ability to consider ourselves and the outside world. It is what most people think of when they hear the term "grey matter."

White matter is buried deep in the brain, while gray matter is mostly found on the brain's surface, or cortex. There is about 50% of each type in the brain. The spinal cord, which transmits nerve impulses to and from the rest of the body, has the opposite arrangement: grey matter at its core with insulating white matter on the outside

The cortex tissue consists mainly of neuron cell bodies, and its folds and fissures (known as gyri and sulci) give the cerebrum its trademark rumped surface. Grey matter contains most of the

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brain's neuronal cell bodies. The grey matter includes regions of the brain involved in muscle control, and sensory perception such as seeing and hearing, memory, emotions, speech, decision making, and self-control. The cerebral cortex has a left and a right hemisphere.

Each hemisphere can be divided into four lobes:

- 1) Frontal lobe
- 2) Temporal lobe
- 3) Occipital lobe
- 4) Parietal lobe

The lobes are functional segments.

They specialize in various areas of thought and memory, of planning and decision making, and of speech and sense perception.

Plate 2: Picture of brain

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Brain Centre that Controls Righting Reflex

Righting reflex is also known as the labyrinthine righting reflex, is a reflex that corrects the orientation of the body when it is taken out of its normal upright position. It is initiated by the vestibular system, which detects that the body is not erect and causes the head to move back into position as the body follows. The perception of head movement involves the body sensing linear acceleration or the force of gravity through the otoliths, and angular acceleration through semi-circular canals. The reflex uses a combination of visual system inputs, vestibular inputs and somatosensory inputs to make postural adjustments when the body becomes displaced from its normal vertical position. These inputs are used to create what is called efferent copy. This means that brain makes comparisons in the cerebellum between expected posture and perceived posture, and corrects for difference. The reflex takes six or seven weeks to perfect, but can be affected by various types of balance disorders (Goldberger and Murray, 1988)

Vestibular system

The vestibular system is composed of inner ear organs forming the "labyrinth": the semicircular canals, the otoliths, and the cochlea. The section below is an overview of the vestibular system, as it is crucial to the understanding of the righting reflex. Sensory information from the vestibular system allows the head to move back into position when disturbed as the rest of the body follows. The semicircular canals (brown, see figure) are arranged at angles to the horizontal plane of the head when it is in its normal vertical posture. Each canal has a widened base, called an ampulla that houses specialized sensory hair cells. Fluid in these canals surrounds the hair cells, and moves across them as the head moves to gather information about the movement and position of the body. The hair cells are covered in tiny sensory hairs called stereocilia, which are sensitive to displacement forces as the body is moved in different positions. When the head is moved, the force moves the hair cells forward, which sends signals to afferent fibers and on to the brain. (Goldberger and Murray, 1988). The brain can then decide which muscles in the body need to become active in order to right itself.

The semicircular canals have a superior, posterior, and horizontal component. Studies have shown that the horizontal canal is most correlated with agility, as shown with several mammals. (Cox PG 2010) Curvature and size of these canals seems to affect agility, and may be due to the environments in which animals navigate, such as a mostly two-dimensional landscape as compared to three-dimensional spaces (i.e. in the air, the trees, or the water). The otoliths have two components: the utricle and the saccule. Both are made of the same sensory tissue containing hair cells, which is covered by a gelatinous layer and the otolithic membrane on top. Embedded in this

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membrane are calcium carbonate crystals, called otoconia, or "ear rocks." As the head is tilted forward or backward, the otoconia move the hair cells in a similar fashion to the semicircular canal fluid movement and cause depolarization of the hair cells. Signals from these cells are also transmitted along afferent fibers and on to the brain. (Goldberger and Murray, 1988)

Signal transduction

Vestibular afferent signals are carried by type I or type II hair cells, which are distinguished by a larger amount of stereocilia per cell in type I cells than in type II cells. (Goldberger and Murray, 1988) Nerve fibers attached to these hair cells carry signals to the vestibular nuclei in the brain, which are then used to gain information about the body's position. Larger diameter afferent fibers carry information from both type I and type II hair cells, and regular afferent fibers carry signals from type II hair cells. (Cullen, KE 2004) The semicircular canals encode head velocity signals, or angular acceleration, while the otoconia encode linear acceleration signals and gravitational signals. Regular afferent signals and irregular afferent signals travel to the vestibular nuclei in the brain, although irregular signals are at least two times more sensitive. Because of this, it has been questioned why humans have regular afferent signals. Studies have shown that regular afferent signals give information about how long the motion of the head or body lasts, and irregular afferent signals occur when the head is moved more violently, such as in falling. (Cullen, KE 2004).

Brain Centers that Control Flexion Reflex

The flexor reflex is a polysynaptic reflex that results in flexor muscle contraction by recruiting flexor muscles across several joints, it is an example of an interjoint reflex that has tissue protective value such as generating quick withdrawal from noxious stimulus. Flexor reflexes are spinal polysynaptic reflexes that can be produced by trains of electrical stimuli delivered to cutaneous or mixed nerves. The normal flexor reflex consists of two EMG components. The first component appears at a higher threshold. The latency of the first component ranges from 50 to 60 min/sec in different individuals, whereas the second component may have a latency of 110 min/sec to more than 400 min/sec, depending upon the strength of the stimulus. Increasing the stimulus strength decreases the latency and increases the duration and amplitude of both components. These reflexes are enhanced in spasticity. The involuntary movements in periodic movements in sleep may be released flexor reflexes.

Flexor/withdrawal reflex

The flexor reflex is a polysynaptic spinal reflex that might be connected with spinal locomotor centers (Bussel *et al.*, 1988). The dominant view is that flexor reflexes are exaggerated after a central nervous lesion and cause muscle spasms after severe spinal cord injury (Ditunno *et al.*,

2004). Also, a spontaneous firing of motor neurons during rest might lead to muscle spasms (Bennett *et al.*, 2004; Gorassini *et al.*, 2004), initially caused by receptor upregulation and later by neuronal sprouting (Goldberger and Murray, 1988).

The increase of flexor reflexes in patients with chronic SCI might represent a marker for neuronal plateau potentials. Furthermore, it seems that the sites where flexor reflexes can be elicited become expanded in patients with a spinal or supraspinal lesion as compared to healthy humans (Schmit *et al.*, 2000; Andersen *et al.*, 2004). Otherwise, a great variability of flexion reflex responses exists in patients with SCI (Muller and Dietz, 2006).

After an acute, complete SCI, flexor reflex excitability and spastic muscle tone develop in parallel. However, after a few months, there is a divergent course in which the severity and occurrence of muscle spasms increase, whereas flexor reflex amplitude decreases (Hiersemenzel *et al.*, 2000). In line with this, patients with complete chronic SCI have a low incidence of the early component of the flexor reflex (Knikou and Conway, 2005) and flexion reflexes produce smaller leg joint torques than those in healthy people. These observations suggest that the activity of flexor reflexes is little related to the occurrence of muscle spasms in spasticity of spinal origin.

Flexion Reflex Pathways

So far, the discussion has focused on reflexes driven by sensory receptors located within muscles or tendons. Other reflex circuitry, however, mediates the withdrawal of a limb from a painful stimulus, such as a pinprick or the heat of a flame. Contrary to what might be imagined, given the speed with which we are able to withdraw from painful stimuli, this flexion reflex involves several synaptic links. As a result of activity in this circuitry, stimulation of nociceptive sensory fibers leads to excitation of ipsilateral flexor muscles and reciprocal inhibition of ipsilateral extensor muscles. Flexion of the stimulated limb is also accompanied by an opposite reaction in the contralateral limb (i.e., the contralateral extensor muscles are excited while flexor muscles are inhibited). This crossed extension reflex serves to enhance postural support during withdrawal of the affected limb from the painful stimulus.

Plate 3: Picture of Spinal cord circuitry responsible for the flexion reflex. (Elsevier B.V 2021)

Spinal cord circuitry responsible for the flexion reflex. Stimulation of cutaneous receptors in the foot leads to activation of spinal cord local circuits that withdraw (flex) the stimulated extremity and extend the other extremity to provide compensatory.

Like the other reflex pathways, local circuit neurons in the flexion reflex pathway receive converging inputs from several different sources, including cutaneous receptors, other spinal cord interneurons, and upper motor neuron pathways. Although the functional significance of this

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complex pattern of connectivity is unclear, changes in the character of the reflex following damage to descending pathways provides some insight. Under normal conditions, a noxious stimulus is required to evoke the flexion reflex; following damage to descending pathways, however, other types of stimulation, such as squeezing a limb, can sometimes produce the same response. This observation suggests that the descending projections to the spinal cord modulate the responsiveness of the local circuitry to a variety of sensory inputs. (Elsevier, 2021).

Disorders to Part of Brain that Controls Reflexes

- i. Ataxia: partial or complete inability to coordinate voluntary movements.
- ii. Epilepsy: Disorders of the CNS that is characterized by temporary disturbances in normal brain impulses; it may be accompanied by convulsive seizures and loss of consciousness
- iii. Huntington disease – Hereditary disorders of the brain producing progressively worsening, uncontrollable dance like movements and personality changes.
- iv. Neuralgia: sharp, recurring pain associated with a nerve, usually caused by inflammation or injury.

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What Can Make Reflexes Dysfunctional

One or a combination of four basic conditions can cause primary infant motor reflex dysfunction or deeper pathology:

- Congenital Disorders
- Trauma
- Prolonged, Intermittent or Chronic Stress
- Non-Congenital Disease

Each of these conditions can cause the central nervous system, sensory system, or motor system to become compromised. Congenital disorders, trauma, and non-congenital disease can also cause innate, neural pathways necessary to engage motor reflex programs to become blocked or damaged.

1. Congenital Disorders

Congenital disorders can occur due to either genetic abnormalities (e.g., color blindness, Downs Syndrome, Cystic Fibrosis) or teratogenic effects, which are maternally related issues that can cause birth defects. These include:

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- Infectious maternal diseases (Aids, Rebella, Syphilis, etc.)
- Chronic maternal conditions (Hypo or Hyperthyroidism, Diabetes, etc.)

Prescriptions, over the counter medications and supplements, or other addictive substances ingested by the mother (alcohol, cigarettes, caffeine, recreational drugs), malnutrition, stress or radiation. Regardless of the cause, when a baby comes into the world with a congenital disorder, there is a possibility that neural pathways necessary to engage innate reflex programs may be blocked or damaged or one of the neurosensory motor systems necessary for primary infant motor reflexes to emerge and function may be impaired.

2. Trauma or Disease

Trauma is defined as an unexpected life-threatening event that results in a debilitating outcome that disrupts normal physical or emotional function. Trauma can result in physical and emotional debilitation. Physical trauma can occur in the womb, during the birth process, at birth or any time after birth, and can be caused by in-utero or birth complications, an accident, violent attack, or natural disaster. Emotional trauma can be caused by neglect, abuse, social isolation, or separation, humiliation, observation of a horrific event, the death of a loved one, or more. If trauma occurs in the womb, or during the typical maturation period of a primary infant motor reflex, neural pathway blockage or damage, or a compromised neurosensory motor system can impact reflex emergence, maturation and integration (Muller and Dietz, 2006).

If life-threatening trauma occurs after a primary reflex pattern has integrated, the autonomic nervous system can trigger primary infant motor reflexes to re-surface as a behavioral adaptation immobilization strategy. In 1994, Stephen Porges proposed as part of his Polyvagal theory that this behavioral adaptation strategy is one of three survival strategies automatically engaged by the autonomic nervous system to ensure the body's survival. Porges's contribution to reflex understanding for more information regarding the body's behavioral adaptation strategies) When a primary infant motor reflex re-surfaces, it often remains present until a knowledgeable resource identifies its presence and uses techniques to foster its integration.

3. Reflex Dysfunction & Prolonged Intermittent or Chronic Stress

The early work of Walter Cannon revealed that the autonomic nervous system manages two general states of function in the body as a normal course of daily function:

- The Non-Alarm State: Managed by the parasympathetic subsystem of the autonomic nervous system. The parasympathetic system. Is responsible for normalizing function in the body during non-alarm states to ensure long-term survival.

- The Alarm State: Managed by the sympathetic subsystem of the autonomic nervous system. Responsible for engaging the mobilization state in the body in order to ensure near-term survival.

These two autonomic subsystems (parasympathetic and sympathetic) function in a symbiotic fashion with one system in more or less control based on the body's internal alarm state. Hans Selye revealed that when the sympathetic nervous system maintains predominate control without allowing the parasympathetic nervous system to restore normative function with regular frequency, not only can the body sustain internal physiological damage, but its overall ability to function effectively, and maintain emotional and behavioral stability, begins to diminish. If this occurs during the typical primary infant motor reflex maturation period, the underlying neurosensory motor function can be challenged making it difficult for the reflex to mature and integrate. If it occurs after all the primary infant motor reflexes have integrated, then low-level trauma, normally managed effectively by the bodies near term survival system, can trigger reflex patterns to re-surface. In other words, prolonged intermittent or chronic stress can compromise maturation and integration of primary infant motor reflexes and can even cause primary infant reflexes to re-surface when a person is faced with low-level trauma.

4. Non-Congenital Disease

Disease that occurs sometime after birth and is not attributable to genetic issues can cause the neural pathway and neurosensory motor system issues previously discussed. If the disease presents itself prior to the typical maturational time period of primary infant motor reflexes or after the infant reflexes have integrated, the same challenges discussed as part of congenital and trauma conditions can occur.

Blocked or Damaged Neural Pathways

When neural pathways are blocked or damaged, the body often attempts to engage innate reflexive motor programs through alternate related pathways. Depending upon the magnitude of the blockage or damage, the resulting primary infant motor reflex may:

- Emerge, mature and integrate with little or no problem or apparent problem (can remain hidden)
- Emerge, not fully mature, and remain dysfunctional present (not integrating)
- Emerge pathologically, functioning in a strange and unexpected fashion (not integrating)
- Simply not emerge

The work of Alexander Luria helped to demonstrate that blocked neural pathways can be “de-inhibited” (activated), and damaged pathways restored through functionally related pathways in the brain. Because innate motor reflex programs are genetically programmed regardless of the challenges that may be present, function can be improved and sometimes even restored when neural pathways are de-inhibited or restored through functionally related pathways. The results depend upon the magnitude of the issues that are present.

5. Motor System

As a result of congenital or traumatic events, a motor response can range from being dysfunctional to pathological. A dysfunctional motor response can be hyperactive, causing too much muscle tension, overdeveloped muscle tone, and muscles too rigid to allow adequate extension, restricting the functional range of movement; or hypoactive, causing too little muscle tension, underdeveloped muscle tone, and muscles too soft to control or support the body. A pathological motor response, more severe in nature than a dysfunctional response, may be:

- Reversed – The opposite of what is expected
- Incorrect – A response expected for some other stimulus
- A-reflexic – generating no response at all

A primary infant motor reflex that exhibits either a dysfunctional or pathological motor response will not be appropriately integrated.

6. Central Nervous System (CNS)

Under normal conditions, the CNS actively fulfills its role mediating the appropriate reactions to sensory signals inside and outside the body to ensure basic bodily functions and activities remain well regulated. Due to congenital defects, trauma or disease, or long-term intermittent or chronic stress, CNS performance can be compromised causing incoming sensory information to be blocked or misinterpreted (under or over exaggerated) and outgoing directives to produce motor responses that are dysfunctional (hypo- or hyperactive, under or over-reactive) or pathological (a-reflexic, incorrect or reversed). For this reason the presence of developmentally inappropriate primary infant motor reflexes has long been viewed, by medical professionals, as an indication of possible neurological issues. (Svetlana Masgutova Educational Institute 2021)

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Plant Materials: Sample of *Musa paradisiaca* (plantain) were obtained from Angwa-tofa, Karu Local Government, Abuja, Nigeria. And identified and vouchered by Ihuma, J. O. Department of Biological Sciences, Bingham University, Karu. Nasarawa State, Nigeria.

Animal Groupings: The animals were grouped into four, five rats per cage, Group 1: animals serve as control group (distilled water and rat chow), Group 2: animals feed with plantain diet 10mg/kg weight of rat, Group 3: animals feed with plantain diet 20mg/kg weight of rat and Group 4: animals feed with plantain diet 30mg/kg weight of rat

Righting Test for Reflex: Righting Reflexes (tests pons and mesencephalon) - (a) when the rat is put on its back, it turns over immediately; (b) the animals is held in the lower back; when the body is tilted, its head moves opposite; (c) the rat is on its back when its head is tilted, its limbs move opposite; (d) when the rat is dropped, upside down, at an 40cm it lands right-side up. (David E. TUPPER and Robert B. WALLACE, Laboratory of Developmental Psychobiology. University of Hartford, West Hartford, Connecticut 06117, USA)

Flexion Reflex: (Tests spinal cord) - The rat is picked up and the toes are pinched with forceps. The response is to move the foot away. (Robert B. WALLACE, Laboratory of Developmental Psychobiology. University of Hartford, West Hartford, Connecticut 06117, USA)

Animal Sacrifice: Retro-orbital also referred to as peri-orbital, posterior orbital and orbital sinus bleeding. Retro-orbital bleeding. Blood is collected from the venous sinus. The rat was restrained, the neck gently scuffed and the eye made to bulge. A capillary tube or pipette is inserted medially, laterally or dorsally. Blood is allowed to flow by capillary action into the capillary tube and into the sample bottles. The sample obtained is a mixture of venous blood and tissue fluid, and is representative of venous blood. (Jo EJ *et al.*, 2021). The blood collected was then spinned in the centrifuge and serum was removed and placed into another test tube and refrigerated.

Determination of Serotonin Level: For serotonin test blood sample is needed, test is done when carcinoid syndrome is suspected. Which are symptoms associated with carcinoid tumours. Tumours of small intestine, colon, appendix and bronchial tubes in the lungs. Normal range of serotonin is 50-200ng/mL (0.28 to 1.14 μ mol/L). Result higher than normal level may indicated carcinoid syndrome (Goldberger and Murray, 1988)

Determination of Adrenaline Level: Adrenaline test is performed on a sample of blood or on sample of urine to measure the level of adrenaline secretion and diagnose whether it is normal for the body. A discrepancy of resultant level with the adrenaline level might be indicative of some serious problems. Normal range for adrenaline in the body should be less than 900pg/ml. if the adrenaline level in the test results is between 0-900pg/ml, there is nothing to worry about since it is the normal level of adrenaline however if it exceeds 900pg/ml the matter requires medical attention as soon as possible. (med line plus)

RESULTS

Test for Serotonin

Figure 1 shows the effects of plantain diet on serotonin level in female wistar rats. The values are represented as mean±SEM. The results shows no statistical significance but there was a relevant decrease in rats fed with 20mg/kg of plantain stock (group 3) (12.92 ± 2.79) and rats fed with 10mg/kg (group 2) (11.21 ± 1.20) compared to the control group (15.72 ± 4.15). And a significant increase in levels in rats fed with 30mg/kg of plantain stock (19.36 ± 2.64).

Figure 1: Graph of serotonin

Test for Adrenaline

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Figure 2 shows the effects of plantain diet on adrenaline level in female wistar rats. The values are represented as mean±SEM. The results shows that there is was a decrease in the level of adrenalin in rats fed with 10mg/kg of plantain stock (group 2) (90.87±9.75). The 30mg/kg (group 4) has the highest level of adrenaline level (156.96± 21.39). Shows a decrease level in the 20mg/kg (group 3) (104.74± 22.65) and 10mg/kg (group 2) (90.87± 9.75) compared to the control group (127.45±33.64).

Figure 2: Graph of Adrenaline

Test for Righting Reflex and Flexion Reflex

Figure 3 and Figure 4 shows the effect of plantain stock on the reflex action in female wistar rat. The values are represented in mean±SEM. The results show that there was a significant decrease in the time taken for the righting reflex and they all spent the same time for the flexion reflex test. The group that received the highest amount of plantain stock 30mg/kg (group 4) had the lowest amount of time on the first trial day (1.31±0.06) which is not statistically significant but decreased significantly on the second day trial (0.85 ± 0.03).

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Figure 3: Day1 flexion and righting reflex tests

Figure 4: Day 2 flexion and righting reflex test

DISCUSSION

Flexion Reflex: Is a spinal reflex intended to protect the body from damaging stimuli. The reflex rapidly coordinates the contraction of all flexion muscles and relaxation of all flexor muscles. Serotonin a hormone has effects on the motor neurons and change in contraction rate of muscle. (Solomon 1990). Results showed no statistical difference but showed a decrease in the levels of serotonin in rats fed with 10mg/kg (group 2) of plantain stock and rats administered 20mg/kg (group 3) of plantain stock when compared with the control group (group 1) and an increase in rats fed with 30mg/kg (group 4) when compared with control group (group 1). These results are not in line with the work done by Young and Teff (1989) on the effects of diet containing unripe plantain on brain serotonin in mice which equally showed significant increase in the level of serotonin in brain of mice. This because of the difference in number of days of treatment and the mode of administration and the type of animals used and the part tested in. while the results of the research conducted only showed an increase in the rat fed with 30mg/kg (group 4) of plantain stock when compared with control group results of Young and Teff showed an increase in serotonin level of mice across all groups.

Righting Reflex: The righting reflex is the reflex that corrects the orientation of the body when it is taken out of its normal upright position it is initiated by vestibular system. The reflex takes 6 weeks to perfect but can be affected by various types of balance disorders. (Wazen 2004). Adrenaline acts on the body by redistributing blood to the muscles and alternating the body's metabolism. In this research results showed no significant difference in that the level of the adrenaline but showed a decrease in rats fed with 10mg/kg (group 2) and 20mg/kg (group 3) of plantain stock when compared to the control group (group 1), also showed an increase in the rats fed with 30mg/kg (group 4) of plantain stock when compared to the control group (group 1).

Conclusion

In conclusion, plantain diet did not have an effect on serotonin and adrenaline in female wistar rats. This is possible the quantity of serotonin and adrenaline in plantain diet is less than the serotonin and adrenaline in the body. There is also a possibility that effects were not seen because of the duration of work. The findings of this research report support the hypothesis that states that plantain diet does not have an effect on reflexes.

Recommendation

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I recommend that further studies be carried out to test for the effects of adrenaline and tests on reflexes.

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